

Design of horizontal drains for the mitigation of liquefaction risk

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Abstract

Drainage is one of the most popular protecting measures to mitigate ground liquefaction. Deploying the drains horizontally may be convenient where conventional vertical ones cannot be used, like beneath existing structures. Spacing among drains must be designed to limit the pore pressure build-up during shaking. The usual assumptions of radial consolidation around vertical drains, stemming from the assumption of an infinite number of drains, may not be appropriate for horizontal ones, since the latter are generally arranged in few rows at a shallow depth, especially if drainage at ground level is possible as well. Hence, in this work existing solutions for vertical “earthquake” drains have been modified to take into account such different geometrical features. The solution has been validated against a numerical and experimental set of data, and charts covering a wide range of geometrical layouts, soil properties and seismic actions are finally proposed. They can be used to design the drain spacing that is needed not to exceed a target value of excess pore pressure in the ground.

Keywords: liquefaction, risk mitigation, drainage, horizontal drains, consolidation, design approach.

1. Introduction

Dynamic liquefaction is a phenomenon that may occur during earthquakes in loose and saturated sandy soil. It is induced by the pore water pressure build-up due to ground shaking that causes a significant reduction of soil shear strength and stiffness and potential damage to existing structures. This in turn may lead to economic and social losses, as it happened in recent earthquakes (e.g. Christchurch, New Zealand, 2010, 2011; Emilia, Italy, 2012) (Alessio et al. 2013; Stevenson et al. 2011, Bray et al. 2014). For such reasons, increasing attention

has been recently given to the development of mitigation techniques against soil liquefaction. These techniques generally aim to reduce the build-up of pore water pressure acting on soil state and fabric (i.e. densification, artificial cementation, addition of fines), on the degree of saturation (induced partial saturation, see for instance Mele et al., 2018) or on drainage conditions. The latter mitigation action is typically obtained by the insertion of vertical drains (often called for this application “earthquake drains”) and is one of the most efficient ways to protect existing structures (e.g. Harada et al., 2006). Furthermore, the use of vertical drains poses no technological problems, being made with current tools like gravel columns, small steel cylindric drains and simple tape drains. The insertion of drains into the liquefiable soil modifies the hydraulic boundary conditions. The drains can be considered as zero excess pore pressure surfaces that, if properly spaced, accelerate the consolidation process during seismic shaking, with a beneficial reduction of soil susceptibility to liquefaction. Some design methods based on the solution of radial consolidation are already available in literature to assign drains spacing (Bouckovalas et al., 2009; Seed and Booker, 1976). However, since the current technology considers only vertical drains, the application of this technique to mitigate liquefaction risk for existing buildings implies that they cannot be placed below the structures. In such a way, drainage is enhanced around the structure to protect, but not in the volume of soil underneath it, on which the structure is directly resting. Because of these geometrical constraints, the result is a reduced effectiveness of the technology in the built environment. A possible solution to this technological limitation may be obtained by adopting directional drilling (Allouche et al., 2000) to place horizontal or sub-horizontal drains, made of micro-perforated pipes, directly underneath existing structures. This is a very promising evolution, whose use should not pose critical installation problems, at least as the horizontal drains are shallow (not deeper than 10 m), and their diameter is not very large (not more than 30 cm). Obviously, it is possible to deploy horizontal drains in multiple rows in either a square grid or in a staggered layout, as done for vertical drains. However, while (as previously mentioned) design methods already exist for the latter, for horizontal drains there is a lack of both experimental evidences on their effectiveness and of well-established design approaches. In fact, being the drains horizontal, the radial consolidation around each drain occurs in the vertical plane and may be influenced by the presence of a free-drainage ground horizontal surface or layer at a close distance. Furthermore, the hypothesis of an infinite number of drains implicitly assumed in the design of vertical drains is completely unrealistic for horizontal drains, for which only two or three lines of drains may be placed on site. Starting from these

considerations, this paper extends the design approach proposed for an infinite number of vertical drains by Bouckovalas et al. (2009) to the case of a limited number of shallow horizontal drains.

2. Background on dynamic consolidation

As mentioned above, soil liquefaction is induced in saturated, loose and shallow sandy soil by the build-up of pore water pressure due to cyclic loading in partially or totally undrained condition. When the excess pore pressure equates the initial effective normal stress, the shear strength of cohesionless soils goes to zero. Simultaneously, the shear modulus tends to zero, and considerable deformations can occur even before full liquefaction. Since the pore pressure increments due to seismic excitation are caused by the volumetric – distortional coupling of soil constitutive behaviour, advanced constitutive models should be used to simulate the complex coupled hydro-mechanical consolidation process. In common practice, however, this is never the adopted procedure, and simplifications are introduced to evaluate the seismically induced pore pressure increments. If the design goal is the limitation of pore pressure build-up to a desired, limit value, a simple uncoupled approach can be adopted to design a drainage system. The consolidation process is then usually solved in the hypothesis of Terzaghi-Rendulic (Rendulic, 1936). In plane strain conditions, it reads:

$$\frac{k}{\gamma_w} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) = m_v \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where x and y are the spatial coordinates in the plane, k is the hydraulic conductivity (assumed isotropic), u is the excess pore pressure and m_v is the volumetric compressibility coefficient. The hypothesis of isotropic permeability is reasonable in the case of sandy soils, interested by liquefaction issues. As previously mentioned, in the case of ongoing cyclic loading, the quantification of u is a very complex problem, being it the resultant of concurrent dissipation (due to consolidation) and increment (due to cyclic shaking). A fundamental contribution to the solution was given by Seed et al. (1975), who proposed to write eq. (1) modifying its right-hand term as the algebraic sum of the change ∂u taking place in the time interval, ∂t , because of the consolidation process, plus an accumulation term related to the ongoing seismic shaking. By so doing, eq. (1) becomes

$$\frac{k}{\gamma_w} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) = m_v \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial u_g}{\partial N} \frac{\partial N}{\partial t} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where u_g is the pore pressure increment generated during shaking and ∂N is the number of cycles taking place in the time interval, ∂t . Within this framework, that is by far the most popular one adopted to study the dynamic

consolidation of soils, different choices can be done to quantify the cyclic pore pressure build up ($\partial u_g / \partial N$). Seed et al. (1975) proposed to this aim a function of the ratio N_{eq}/N_l between the seismic action, quantified through the number of equivalent cycles, N_{eq} , and the number of cycles required to cause liquefaction, N_l . Analysing the experimental results on shaking table by Harada et al. (2006), however, Bouckovalas et al. (2009) observed that the pore water pressure build-up at the early stages of cyclic loading depends mainly on soil fabric evolution and not on r_u . In order to cope with this experimental evidence, they proposed a different equation for $\partial u_g / \partial N$:

$$\frac{\partial u_g}{\partial N} = \frac{\sigma'_0}{\pi A N_l} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{t}{t_d} \frac{N_{eq}}{N_l}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{2A}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} r_u\right)} \quad (3)$$

where σ'_0 is the initial vertical effective stress, A is an empirical parameter affecting the shape of the accumulation curve, t is the time variable, t_d is the significant duration of seismic shaking, r_u is the excess pore pressure ratio (u_g / σ'_0).

In the hypothesis of a linear dependency of the number of cycles on time, it can be written that:

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = \frac{N_{eq}}{t_d} \quad (4)$$

Hence, by substituting (3) and (4) in (2), and using dimensionless variables, the following form of the equation of consolidation is obtained:

$$T_{ad} \left(\frac{\partial^2 r_u}{\partial \left(\frac{x}{d}\right)^2} + \frac{\partial^2 r_u}{\partial \left(\frac{y}{d}\right)^2} \right) = \frac{\partial r_u}{\partial \left(\frac{t}{t_d}\right)} - \frac{N_{eq}}{\pi A N_l} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{N_{eq}}{N_l} \frac{t}{t_d}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{2A}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} r_u\right)} \quad (5)$$

where d is the drain diameter and T_{ad} is a dimensionless time factor defined as:

$$T_{ad} = \frac{t_d k}{d^2 m_v \gamma_w} \quad (6)$$

in which γ_w is the specific weight of water. T_{ad} is a non-dimensional time, expressed as a function of a given drain diameter (d) and of a specific site seismic hazard through the significant seismic duration (t_d).

3. Numerical model

In this paper, eq. (5) has been used to solve the dynamic consolidation process considering the existence of horizontal drains, with the final goal to draw simple design charts to assign the spacing among them.

The geometrical layout of the problem considered in this work is shown in Fig. 1. The model is representative of a homogeneous layer of liquefiable soil; the analysis of more complex soil profiles would be hard to generalize and thus it is beyond the purposes of this paper. In the domain, three rows of drains (each one made of an infinite number of constantly spaced drains) are deployed in a staggered arrangement (*'quincunces'*). H' is the distance from the upper boundary to the upper row of drains. As shown in Fig. 1, the layout is defined by the spacing between the drains, s , and the angle α (assumed equal to 60° , as typical in this configuration). The numerical analyses have been carried out considering all the dimensions normalized to the inner diameter of the drains d (Fig 1a). The lower boundary, assumed impervious, is located at a depth of $2s/d$ from the lower row of drains. Its position has been chosen far enough from the drains not to affect the solution. Taking advantage of symmetry, the analyses have been carried out with reference to a numerical domain of reduced area (Fig. 1a). The left and right boundaries of such a domain are defined by two impervious planes of symmetry (Fig. 1a).

Fig. 1. (a) numerical model domain; (b) numerical solution domain; (c) numerical solution domain with increased s/d .

The upper boundary is represented by a surface with zero excess pore water pressure. Along the impervious vertical sides of the model, the drains are modelled as segments with zero excess pore water pressure. Rigorously, this hydraulic boundary condition should be applied on the inner surface of the drain and some authors showed that drain hydraulic resistivity is not negligible in calculations, since it can affect the

consolidation process (Onoue, 1988). However, horizontal drains are likely made of microperforated pipes, and thus their longitudinal hydraulic resistivity is negligible compared to the cross-sectional permeability of the pipe, which is higher than that of the soil. In the limiting case of drain permeability equal to that of the soil, the circular ring of the pipe behaves (hydraulically) as a soil layer, and the hypothesis of zero excess pore water pressure applied on the inner surface of drain holds true. If drain equivalent permeability is higher than that of soil, then the hypothesis is obviously conservative.

Even though the solution of the consolidation process is obtained in the whole numerical model domain, the effect of excess pore water pressure dissipation due to the drains is evaluated only in the part of it having thickness H from the upper boundary, being $H=(H'/d+2s/d \cdot \sin \alpha + 0.5 \cdot s/d)$ (Fig. 1b). This assumption stems from the observation that, at a depth equal or higher than $0.5 s/d$ below the lower drains ($z>H$), the pore pressure increments are not affected by the presence of the drains, as shown in the following section. These assumptions infer that by changing the normalized spacing s/d among the drains the geometrical features of both the numerical model and the solution domains are modified (Fig. 1c).

The problem was solved with an implicit finite difference method (Crank et al. 1947; D'Acunto, 2012) discretizing the domain with a rectangular grid. Spatial variables were related to drain diameter to simplify the design approach; as already pointed out, drain diameter is limited by technology, thus it is easy to assign, and, by consequence, H'/d can be determined. Each drain segment was discretized by six nodes. By solving the consolidation problem, it is possible to know the excess pore pressure ratio in each point of the model grid, at a dimensionless time, t/t_d . The problem has been solved in a parametric way by varying the geometrical layout (spacing s/d and distance of the upper surface, H'/d), the soil properties (i.e. the volumetric compressibility coefficient, m_v , and the coefficient of hydraulic conductivity, k) and the parameters defining the seismic action (T_{ad} , N_{eq}/N_l).

4. Numerical results

Once the numerical problem is solved, it is possible to know the excess pore water pressure ratio in each point of the domain. The effect of the horizontal drains on the distribution of r_u in the domain is shown by contours in Fig. 2. It can be observed a high gradient of r_u around drains that is independent on H'/d for the two deeper rows. The effect of the first row of drains is instead dependent on the distance from the upper boundary.

Fig. 2. Contours of excess pore pressure ratio in the solution domain at the end of shaking, with $N_{eq}/N_1=1$, $s/d=10$, $T_{ad}=50$.

When H'/d is lower than s/d , the effect of the upper boundary is predominant on the effect of the drain, lowering its efficiency. When H'/d is equal to s/d , there is almost no overlap between the upper boundary and the first row of drains, and its efficiency is enhanced; this is evident in the contour for $H'/d=5$, where the distribution of r_u in the upper part of the domain is similar to the distribution of $H'/d=10$. Finally, if H'/d is higher than s/d , the drains act almost as a boundary condition, with a lower excess pore pressure ratio, on the upper part of the domain at a distance from the first row almost equal to half of the spacing. In the last case, three areas can be distinguished: an upper part, where the gradients of excess pore pressure ratio are almost vertical, and the behaviour is almost one-dimensional; a middle part, between drains, where r_u is almost constant except for the area surrounding the drains, where the gradients are much higher; the lower part, where the effect of drains vanishes and again the gradients become vertical. When H'/d is lower or equal to s/d , the first two areas are partially overlapped. The contours also show that the excess pore water pressure ratio on a horizontal plane is almost constant except for the depths corresponding to the rows of drains, as already pointed out.

The average and maximum excess pore pressure ratios, respectively $r_{u,mean}(t, y/d)$ and $r_{u,max}(t, y/d)$, were calculated for each depth to quantify the effect of drains. The vertical profiles of these quantities at the end of the analysis are presented in Fig. 3, Fig.4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

In Fig. 3 the effect of drain spacing with $T_{ad}=50$ and $N_{eq}/N_I=1$, is shown for two different values of H'/d . The mean and maximum profiles of $r_u(y/d)$ at the end of shaking are similar, differing more around the depths of drains, with such a difference being a function of drains' spacing: obviously, for closer spacing the effectiveness of drains increases. It is worth noting that when s/d is much smaller than H'/d , the maximum value of r_u is attained in the upper part of the domain, where there is the largest drainage distance. When spacing increases and becomes higher than H'/d , the maximum value is attained in the lower part of the domain.

Fig. 3. Vertical profiles of $r_{u,mean}$ (continuous grey lines) and $r_{u,max}$ (dashed black lines) at the end of shaking, with $T_{ad}=50$ and $N_{eq}/N_I=1$.

In Fig. 4 the vertical profiles of r_u with $T_{ad}=50$, $s/d=10$, $H'/d=10$ and different values of N_{eq}/N_l are plotted. There is a slight difference between $N_{eq}/N_l=0.75$ and $N_{eq}/N_l=1$ and in both cases the excess pore pressure ratio is below 0.6 along the whole vertical. However, when $N_{eq}/N_l=2$, the excess pore pressure ratio is equal to 1 everywhere except for the area above the upper row of drains and around the drains themselves. It must be noted that a value of N_{eq}/N_l lower than 1 implies that during the shaking no liquefaction occurs (r_u is lower than 1), either with or without drains. Although in these cases liquefaction does not occur, the excess pore pressure build-up reduces both shear stiffness and strength of the soil. This induces non-negligible settlements and deformations under existing structures. Therefore, drains are useful also for $N_{eq}/N_l \leq 1$, to reduce pore pressure build-up (or r_u) during shaking.

Fig. 4. Vertical profiles of r_u mean (continuous grey lines) and r_u max (dashed black lines) with $H'/d=10$ and $s/d=10$ at the end of shaking: effect of N_{eq}/N_l with $T_{ad}=50$.

In Fig. 5 (a) and Fig. 5 (b) the effect of T_{ad} is shown. When N_{eq}/N_l is equal to 1, thanks to the drains, liquefaction is impeded even if T_{ad} is as low as 25 and their effect is enhanced significantly when T_{ad} increases. When $N_{eq}/N_l=2$, however, the effect of T_{ad} is much more significant. As a matter of fact, with $s/d=10$ and $H'/d=10$, drains are not able to prevent liquefaction when T_{ad} is low and a smaller spacing is needed.

Fig. 5. Vertical profiles of r_u mean (continuous grey lines) and r_u max (dashed black lines) with $H'/d=10$ and $s/d=10$ at the end of shaking: effect of T_{ad} for $N_{eq}/N_l=1$ and 2.

When increasing H'/d , the efficiency of drains on the upper part of the domain rises up while the effect of the upper boundary surface decreases. The combination of both effects gives a similar profile of r_u above the first row of the drains at varying H'/d ($< s/d$). When H'/d exceeds the value of s/d , the negative effect of the increased distance between the upper boundary and the first row of drains exceeds the positive combined effect of the two boundaries and a higher excess pore pressure ratio is calculated.

Fig. 6. Vertical profiles of $r_{u\max}$ at the end of shaking with $N_{eq}/N_l=1$ and $T_{ad}=25$ (above) and $T_{ad}=200$ (below).

5. Validation of results

The results obtained with the presented numerical model were validated in this study via some FEM simulations with Plaxis2D, calibrating the model to simulate the results of a centrifuge test carried out at ISMGEO (Italy) within the European research project LIQUEFACT (Airoldi et al., 2018). In order to perform the validation accounting for the unavoidable differences between the experimental set up and the geometrical layout considered in this work (Fig. 1), the coupled hydro-mechanical analyses were performed by using UBC3D-PML model (Petalas, 2012). This elastoplastic constitutive model is based on the UBCSand model (Puebla et al., 1997) and simulates the effects of cyclic loading using two yield surfaces of the Mohr-Coulomb type, one linked to isotropic hardening and the other to kinematic hardening. The calibration of the parameters of the constitutive model for the sand has been performed based on the suggestions of Beaty and Byrne (2011), i.e. expressing the parameters as functions of soil relative density. Only the f_{dens} parameter was calibrated based on the cyclic undrained resistance curve (Fioravante et al., 2016), at an appropriate relative density, Dr . The result is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Comparison between experimental and numerical cyclic resistance curve.

The first step of the validation procedure was to simulate the seismic centrifuge test with horizontal drains (Airoldi et al. 2018) whose geometrical configuration is reported in Fig. 8. In the centrifuge, drains were realized by perforated PVC pipes with an external diameter of 6 mm (0.3 m at prototype scale at 50g acceleration) and a thickness of 1 mm. In the numerical analyses, they were modelled as having a finite

permeability (while the solution proposed in this paper assumes for the drains an infinite permeability as above mentioned), whose value was calibrated on a back analysis of the centrifuge test. In the Plaxis model, tied degree of freedom conditions were used for the lateral boundaries, to simulate the true centrifuge boundary conditions. The calibration of the model leads to the set of parameters reported in Table 1.

A standard Italian sand was used for the tests, namely Ticino sand, characterized by a coefficient of permeability $k=2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m/s. The seismic input applied at the base of the model has the characteristics reported in Table 2. For further details on the experimental set up and results, the reader is addressed to the paper by Airolidi et al. (2018).

Fig. 8. Geometry of centrifuge test model (modified after Airolidi et al., 2018).

A good agreement was found with the centrifuge test both in terms of excess pore pressure and acceleration, as shown in Fig. 9 for both the spacings of drains adopted in the centrifuge test.

Table 1. Centrifuge test calibration parameters.

Dr	$N_{1,60}$	e	n	v	K_B^e	K_G^e	K_G^p	m_e	n_e	n_p	φ_{cs}	φ_{peak}	R_f	f_{dens}	$f_{E,post}$
(%)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	(°)	(°)	(-)	(-)	(-)
54.50	13.70	0.73	0.42	0.3	2246.00	1036.00	680.60	0.50	0.50	0.40	33.00	34.40	0.74	9.00	1.00

In order to carry out the validation of the numerical model proposed in this paper, a further step had to be done: once the FEM analyses were proven to be reliable and well calibrated, a further Plaxis2D analysis with the same coupled model was carried out by modelling drains by a zero excess pore pressure surface. In so doing,

the results of FEM analyses can be compared to those obtained with the approach proposed in this paper, for which the drains are modelled as surfaces with infinite permeability (being characterized by zero excess pressure). In this comparison, the FEM analyses will be assumed as the “true” results.

Fig. 9. Comparison between test measurements and FEM model results: acceleration spectra; excess pore pressure history.

In order to carry out the comparison, the volumetric compressibility coefficient (m_v) required to determine T_{ad} , was derived from an isotropic compression curve at an isotropic compressive stress equal to 50 kPa; the number of equivalent cycles, N_{eq} was calculated based on the procedure suggested by Biondi et al. (2012). The number of cycles required to cause liquefaction was derived by the cyclic resistance curve; the Cyclic Stress Ratio (CSR) was calculated based on the approach proposed by Seed et al. (1975) with the maximum acceleration at ground surface derived by a dynamic total stress analysis. CSR is a function of the depth and by consequence, also N_l is a function of z ; thus, a representative depth has to be assumed to assign N_{eq}/N_l . In a design procedure, the depth would be set at the middle of the layer that has to be treated. Hence, the depth was set at the middle

of numerical solution domain (Fig. 1b), that is equal to 2.3 m and 4 m for $s/d = 5$ and $s/d = 10$, respectively. The upper boundary with zero excess pore pressure is represented by the water table, thus H'/d (dimensionless distance between upper boundary and first row of drains) is equal to 4.33.

Table 2. Earthquake characteristics; T_r is the return period, M_w is the moment magnitude, R_{ep} is the epicentral distance, t_d is the significant duration, a_{max} refers to maximum acceleration at the bottom of centrifuge model.

Source file (-)	T_r (years)	M_w (-)	R_{ep} (km)	t_d (s)	a_{max} (g)
ESM EU.HRZ..HNE.D.19790415.061941.C.ACC.ASC	2475	6.9	62.9	18.67	0.18

Fig. 10 shows excess pore pressure ratio vertical profiles related to three vertical sections (left boundary, right boundary and middle section of simplified model). The curves are very similar and show an almost constant distribution of excess pore pressure ratio on the horizontal direction.

Table 3. Parameters for numerical model; r_d is the shear stress reduction factor that accounts for dynamic response of the soil profile (Idriss, 1999), CSR is the cyclic stress ratio at depth z ; a_{max} refers to the acceleration at the top of centrifuge model, k , and m_v are permeability and volumetric compressibility coefficient of soil.

s/d (-)	a_{max} (g)	z (m)	r_d (-)	CSR (-)	N_1 (-)	N_{eq}/N_1 (-)	k (m/s)	m_v (1/MPa)	T_{ad} (-)
5	0.159	2.3	0.98	0.214	1.2	14	1.7E-03	0.05	689
10		4	0.96	0.209	1.6	11			

The profiles are reported for two instants, related to the time at which maximum excess pore pressure ratio was observed in FE analysis, and at the end of earthquake significant duration. The dashed lines represent the bottom of the solution domain that is used to produce the design charts. A very good agreement can be observed on $s/d=5$ at both times along all the vertical profile. The vertical profiles at $s/d=10$ are quite similar from the top surface to the central row of drains, but numerical analysis overestimates significantly excess pore pressure ratio in the lower part of the domain, that is deeper compared to the case $s/d=5$; this is due to the assumption that CSR is constant with depth, while it should decrease with depth. Thus, the proposed numerical approach overestimates the pore pressure build up in depth compared to the reference FE dynamic analysis. Furthermore, once excess pore pressure ratio achieves unity, the build-up of pore water pressure, $\partial u_g/\partial t$, given by eq. (3) is much higher than the dissipation due to drains, $\partial u/\partial t$, and thus the reduction of r_u calculated in the coupled dynamic analysis performed in Plaxis is not well captured in the numerical analysis.

However, the simplification considered in the proposed method leads to a conservative design approach, and the procedure can be thus considered validated.

Fig. 10. Vertical profiles of excess pore pressure ratio for s/d equal to 5 and 10 at two times ($t^*=t/t_d$). Continuous and dashed lines refer to Plaxis and numerical analyses, respectively.

6. Design method for horizontal drains

The purpose of the paper is to define a simple and straightforward method to design a set of horizontal drains for the mitigation of soil liquefaction. Thus, the results of the previously commented analyses were summarised in design charts. An example is shown in Fig. 11, the other charts are collected below (Fig. 12, Fig. 13 and Fig. 14). The charts represent the excess pore pressure ratio in the solution domain for different sets of parameters. For each instant t , the mean and maximum excess pore pressure ratios in the solution domain were evaluated. Because of the seepage induced by the hydraulic gradients around drains, the worst conditions are not necessarily attained at the end of the shaking, being possible to observe them during the shaking. Therefore, the maximum values in time of the mean and maximum excess pore pressure ratios calculated over the whole domain, $r_{u,mean}$ and $r_{u,max}$, were considered in the design charts. Each one of them is related to specific values of the ratios H'/d and N_{eq}/N_i ; each curve refers to a value of T_{ad} and represents the excess pore pressure ratio (as explained before) for different values of s/d . The use of the charts requires the definition of N_{eq} and t_d . Both these parameters are related to the seismic hazard of the site, and in literature different ways to quantify them are available (e.g. Green and Terri, 2005; Trifunac and Brady, 1975). To quantify T_{ad} , the hydraulic and

mechanical properties of the liquefiable soil (in terms of volumetric compressibility m_v and hydraulic conductivity coefficient k) and the drain diameter must be defined. Finally, it is necessary to know the soil resistance to liquefaction in terms of the number of equivalent constant amplitude cycles that lead to liquefaction, N_l . Hence the ratio N_{eq}/N_l may be calculated. Once the depth of the first row of drains, H' , is chosen, the ratio H'/d can be calculated and the related chart (for a given value of N_{eq}/N_l) can be selected, while the curve to be used is defined by T_{ad} .

Fig. 11. Design charts for $H'/d=10$ and $N_{eq}/N_l=1$.

The last step is the definition of the design target for the mean (or maximum) r_u . Its value can be decided based on a reference limit state. Generally, r_u is chosen referring to the allowable settlements or to the bearing capacity of shallow foundations.

Finally, once the target excess pore pressure ratio r_u is defined, a dimensionless spacing s/d can be obtained from the relevant chart.

An application can be carried out using the chart shown in Fig. 11, for $H'/d=10$, $T_{ad}=50$ and $N_{eq}/N_l=1$. Supposing that the design mean excess pore pressure ratio $r_{u,mean}$ is equal to 0.4, from the chart the design spacing s/d is around 11.5. Given the spacing, it is possible to verify that the value of $r_{u,max}$ is acceptable: in this case it is equal to 0.69. It is worth noting that the s/d obtained from the design chart is almost equal to H'/d , which means that the maximum excess pore pressure ratio is likely to be achieved in the lower part of the domain, as discussed before.

Fig. 12. Design charts for $H'/d=5$.

Fig. 13. Design charts for $H'/d=10$.

Fig. 14. Design charts for $H'/d=15$.

7. Conclusions

The efficacy of horizontal drains as a measure to reduce pore pressure build-up during shaking in liquefiable soils has been analysed in the paper. The existing design criteria for vertical drains were modified to cope with the different geometrical layout of horizontal drains that affects the consolidation process. The problem was solved with an implicit finite difference algorithm and the results were summarised in charts, plotting the calculated peak excess pore pressure ratio r_u (both mean and maximum values in the domain), for different values of the demand to capacity ratio (N_{eq}/N_{liq}) and of the dimensionless time factor (T_{ad}) that accounts for the significant seismic duration (t_d). It is worth noticing that the numerical analyses carried out in this paper have some limitations. First of all, only one geometrical layout was considered (three rows of drains); then, a soil having isotropic permeability and drains for which well resistance could be neglected have been considered.

Notwithstanding these limitations, that at least for the constitutive part are typical of the existing solutions, the proposed design method can be adopted also when significant pore-pressure build-up is expected, but liquefaction is not reached (i.e. $N_{eq}/N_{liq} < 1$). In this case, the design target (i.e. the limit value of the excess pore-pressure ratio, r_u) should be selected as the one neither triggering an unacceptable reduction of the bearing capacity nor causing excessive settlements of the structure for which liquefaction risk has to be mitigated.

Within the large number of ground improvement technologies that can be used to tackle liquefaction risk, horizontal drains are an interesting and innovative option to be adopted in the built environment, as they can be put in place via directional drilling underneath existing buildings with little or no soil disturbance. As a consequence, the proposed design charts can be of great interest to the practitioners.

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Notation

A: shape parameter for pore pressure build-up curve;

d: drain diameter;

H'/d : dimensionless distance from the upper boundary of the domain to the first row of drains;

N: number of cycles;

N_{eq} : number of equivalent cycles of the shaking;

N_f : number of cycles required to cause liquefaction;

r_u : excess pore pressure ratio;

t: time variable;

T_{ad} : dimensionless time factor;

t_d : significant duration of the shaking;

u_g : generated excess pore pressure;

γ_w : specific weight of water;

σ'_0 : initial normal effective stress.

References

- Airoidi, S., Fioravante, V., Giretti, D., Moglie, J., 2018. Validation of liquefaction retrofitting techniques from geotechnical centrifuge small scale models [WWW Document]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.1281598>
- Alessio, G., Alfonsi, L., Brunori, C.A., Burrato, P., Casula, G., Cinti, F.R., Civico, R., Colini, L., Cucci, L., De Martini, P.M., Falcucci, E., Galadini, F., Gaudiosi, G., Gori, S., Mariucci, M.T., Montone, P., Moro, M., Nappi, R., Nardi, A., Nave, R., Pantosti, D., Patera, A., Pesci, A., Pezzo, G., Pignone, M., Pinzi, S., Pucci, S., Salvi, S., Tolomei, C., Vannoli, P., Venuti, A., Villani, F., 2013. Liquefaction phenomena associated with the Emilia earthquake sequence of May-June 2012 (Northern Italy). *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 13, 935–947. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-13-935-2013>
- Allouche, E.N., Ariaratnam, S.T., Lueke, J.S., 2000. Horizontal directional drilling: Profile of an emerging industry. *J. Constr. Eng. Manag.* 126, 68–76.
- Beaty, M.H., Byrne, P.M., 2011. UBCSAND CONSTITUTIVE MODEL Version 904aR, Itasca UDM Web

Site.

- Biondi, G., Cascone, E., Di Filippo, G., 2012. Affidabilità di alcune correlazioni empiriche per la stima del numero di cicli di carico equivalente. *Riv. Ital. di Geotec.* 46, 9–39.
- Bouckovalas, G., Papadimitriou, A., Niarchos, D., 2009. Gravel drains for the remediation of liquefiable sites. *Performance-Based Des. Earthq. Geotech. Eng.* <https://doi.org/10.1201/NOE0415556149.ch4>
- Bray, J., Cubrinovski, M., Zupan, J., Taylor, M., 2014. Liquefaction effects on buildings in the central business district of Christchurch. *Earthq. Spectra* 30, 85–109. <https://doi.org/10.1193/022113EQS043M>
- Crank, J., Nicolson, P., Hartree, D.R., 1947. A practical method for numerical evaluation of solutions of partial differential equations of the heat-conduction type. *Math. Proc. Cambridge Philos. Soc.* 43, 50. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0305004100023197>
- D’Acunto, B., 2012. *Computational partial differential equations for engineering sciences*. Nova Science Publishers, New York.
- Green, R., Terri, G., 2005. Number of Equivalent Cycles Concept for Liquefaction Evaluations—Revisited. *J. Geotech. Geoenvironmental Eng.* 131, 477–488. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(2005\)131:4\(477\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2005)131:4(477))
- Harada, N., Towhata, I., Takatsu, T., Tsunoda, S., Sesov, V., 2006. Development of new drain method for protection of existing pile foundations from liquefaction effects. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 26, 297–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2005.02.019>
- Idriss, I.M., 1999. An update to the Seed-Idriss simplified procedure for evaluating liquefaction potential. *Proc., TRB Workshop New Approaches to Liq. Publ. n. FHWA-RD-99-165, Fed. Highw. Administration.*
- Mele, L., Tian, J.T., Lirer, S., Flora, A., Koseki, J., 2018. Liquefaction resistance of unsaturated sands: experimental evidence and theoretical interpretation. *Géotechnique* 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.18.P.042>
- Onoue, A., 1988. Diagrams considering well resistance for designing spacing. *Soils Found.* 2091. <https://doi.org/10.1248/cpb.37.3229>
- Petalas, A., 2012. *PLAXIS LIQUEFACTION MODEL UBC3D-PLM.*
- Puebla, H., Byrne, P.M., Phillips, R., 1997. Analysis of CANLEX liquefaction embankments: prototype and centrifuge models. *Can. Geotech. J.* 34, 641–657. <https://doi.org/10.1139/t97-034>

- Rendulic, L., 1936. Porenziffer und porenwasserdruck in tonen. *Der Bauingenieur* 17, 559–564.
- Seed, H.B., Booker, J.R., 1976. Stabilization of potentially liquefiable sand deposits using gravel drains. *ASCE, J. Geotech. Eng. Div.* <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- Seed, H.B., Idriss, I.M., Makdisi, F., Banerjee, N., 1975. Representation of irregular stress time histories by equivalent uniform stress series in liquefaction analyses. Rep. No. EERC 75-29, Earthq. Eng. Res. Center, Univ. California, Berkeley, Calif. 40 pp.
- Seed, H.B., Martin, P.P., Lysmer, J., 1975. The generation and dissipation of pore water pressures during soil liquefaction. College of Engineering, University of California.
- Stevenson, J.R., Kachali, H., Whitman, Z., Seville, E., Vargo, J., Wilson, T., 2011. Preliminary observations of the impacts the 22 February Christchurch earthquake had on organisations and the conomy: A Report from the Field (22 February-22 March 2011). *Bull. New Zeal. Soc. Earthq. Eng.* 44, 65.
- Trifunac, M.D., Brady, A.G., 1975. A study on the duration of strong earthquake ground motion. *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Am.* 65, 581–626. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-9062\(76\)90487-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-9062(76)90487-3)